

A Study on the Performance of SOTA LLMs on Nepalese IOE Entrance Examination

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ABSTRACT:

Large language models have extensively been evaluated on standardized tests across high-resource settings, including studies in India, the United States, and other nations. However, their performance on entrance examinations in low-resource countries, such as Nepal, remains less explored. This study evaluates four state-of-the-art (SOTA) LLMs: ChatGPT (gpt-5-2025-08-07), Claude (claude-opus-4.1-20250805), Gemini (gemini-2.5-pro), and DeepSeek (deepseek-chat), on multiple-choice questions from the Tribhuvan University (TU) Institute of Engineering (IOE) entrance examination in Nepal, where subjects included are Mathematics, Physics, Chemistry, and English. We assessed both the overall percentage points scored and the responses across categories and systematic behavioral patterns in the answers received. Results showed that the percentage points scored ranged from 77.24% to 85.77%, which is considerably above average performance compared to past trends among human test takers. Performance varied notably by subject, with Chemistry having the highest correct responses (85.71%-92.86%) and Mathematics having the lowest (72.16%-80.11%). Counterintuitively, English underperformed despite LLMs being mainly trained on natural language data. Statistical analysis showed position-dependent patterns, with questions having correct answers at position 4 showing 78.4% higher odds of being correct across all models. Chi-square tests identified significant option-selection bias only in DeepSeek when the answer provided was incorrect. These findings indicate that while LLMs demonstrate above-average competency on the IOE entrance examination, they still exhibit systematic biases in their responses.

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INTRODUCTION

The past decade has delivered a remarkable advance in machine learning, driven in large part by exponential advances in neural network architecture and hardware. From the foundational work on convolutional neural networks to the breakthroughs in attention mechanism-based networks, the field has progressed through successive waves of innovation [1]. Among the most consequential of these developments has been the emergence of large language models; systems trained on vast text corpora that demonstrate fluency in generation, translation, summarization, and question answering and other tasks [2], [5]. Beyond unstructured text applications, recent studies have also begun exploring the integration of large language models with structured and tabular data to enhance predictive performance in domain-specific problems, such as material corrosion rate estimation using hybrid LLM and machine learning frameworks [3], [4]. These models have now fully moved from research laboratories into widespread deployment, reshaping workflows in industries ranging from customer service to legal document review. However, caught in this wave is our limited understanding of their capabilities and limitations, even when they appear to be extraordinarily capable [6].

Standardized testing, especially in an academic setting, offers one such lens for examining their capabilities. The relative complexity and strict nature of such exams make them an ideal substrate for LLM testing [7]. To obtain high scores on academic tests, models should possess extensive knowledge on the subject matter and have a good problem-solving capability [8]. Evaluation on such examinations can reveal whether strong performance reflects genuine problem-solving or memorization of training data, a concern that has received increasing attention as benchmark data contamination has emerged as a significant challenge in accurate model performance assessment, as the model makers have included more and more data in their training corpus [9].

Nepal's IOE entrance examination provides a setting where this contamination concern is reduced. The exam administered by TU covers Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics, and English (PCME), with content drawn from the nation's Grade 11 and 12 science curriculum. IOE questions are not officially published even after the examination; hence, to the best of our knowledge, they have not been digitized on the public internet.

The objectives of this study are threefold. Firstly, we assess whether these models achieve passing-level performance, establishing a baseline for comparison with average human performance. Secondly, we characterize subject-wise performance hierarchies to identify domains of relative strength and weakness, examining whether observed patterns align with or diverge from theoretical expectations. Thirdly, we investigate systematic patterns in model responses, including option-position preferences and non-response tendencies, to try to understand the factors influencing LLM behavior on structured assessments. Together, these analyses aim to contribute to empirical findings relevant to educational technology applications. As well as work as a preliminary, suggestive guide for students using these models as study partners while preparing for tests.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the last few years, large language models have started to reshape how we think about learning and assessment [10]. Early discussions, notably Kasneci et al. (2023), showed that models such as GPT-3 and GPT-4 could explain concepts clearly, generate practice questions, and even mimic the style of one-on-one tutoring. These early reflections created excitement, but they also emphasized

something important: these models can be helpful, but only when used thoughtfully and with caution. They are powerful, yet sometimes make confident mistakes or rely on surface-level patterns rather than a genuine understanding of the subject matter at hand [11]. A commonly used term for such a pitfall is hallucination.

The general visibility of LLMs in education increased when GPT-4 achieved passing-level performance on United States Medical License Examination (USMLE) style medical questions. Scoring around 86% on Step-1 type items, GPT-4 demonstrated that with rapid advancements and more parameters and data points new models could handle large, content-heavy medical domains questions fairly well. This triggered a wave of conversations about whether LLMs could realistically support professional education or exam preparation [12]. Subsequent systematic reviews have documented that ChatGPT's performance varies substantially across different medical licensing examinations worldwide, with GPT-4 consistently outperforming GPT-3.5, though neither version performs uniformly across all contexts [13].

In the meantime, benchmark efforts such as the Massive Multitask Language Understanding (MMLU) evaluation documented that large GPT-3 models could perform across a surprisingly wide range of subjects (57), spanning from physics to history [8], which opened a door for argument to be made that LLMs could be considered as general academic assistants rather than niche tools. However, strong performance on structured benchmark datasets does not necessarily translate to success on the messy, demanding nature of real examinations, where question formats, cultural contexts, and domain-specific reasoning requirements can differ substantially from training distributions.

As these optimistic results circulated, another set of studies painted a more cautious picture: models sometimes look smarter than they really are. For example, researchers found that many LLMs have built-in preferences for certain multiple-choice options, like picking "A" more often than others, and that simply changing the order of answer choices could cause change in accuracy (or score). In some cases, a simple re-ordering of the options caused accuracy to change by more than half. These findings mean that an LLM's "score" can sometimes reflect formatting quirks more than actual reasoning [12]. Banjade et al. (2024) similarly showed that deep-learning and generative-model excel at structured pattern-recognition tasks, reinforcing the broader distinction between strong pattern-matching abilities and the more uncertain reasoning capabilities of current LLMs [14]. Researchers also noticed that LLMs do not always behave like humans when answering structured questions. Even small, irrelevant changes in wording can nudge their answers in odd directions, making it tricky to interpret why the model chose a certain response or what type of "thinking" it was doing [12].

This discussion becomes more nuanced when looking at studies from South Asian exams, where the question styles often are different from Western contexts. A few studies from India provide a starting point. On an undergraduate community-medicine exam, ChatGPT-3.5 scored about 66%, which is above the passing mark and even competitive with students. This suggests that in subjects where questions focus heavily on content knowledge, LLMs can perform fairly well [15]. Another study looked at the National Eligibility cum Entrance Test (NEET) in 2023 premedical exam and compared GPT-3.5, GPT-4, and Bard (now renamed to Gemini). GPT-4 performed best out of the three, though the differences between models were noticeable. This shows two things: LLMs could handle certain Indian entrance exam formats; but also, the results depend considerably on which version of the model is used [16].

Similarly, the performance of LLMs changed considerably when a study was conducted on their ability to solve Joint Entrance Exam (JEE) Advanced level exams, an undergraduate level entrance exam for engineering in India. On a large set of JEE Advanced style questions (the JEEBench benchmark), even the strongest models scored below 40%. Despite giving them chain-of-thought reasoning prompts, the models still struggled with symbolic algebra, multi-step physics problems, and questions requiring precise mathematical understanding and reasoning. The authors found that fluency in language was unable to compensate for weaknesses in step-by-step problem solving of the models used [17].

Specifically in Nepal, two recent studies provide context for the present work. Luitel et al. (2025) evaluated ChatGPT-4 on the Nepal Medical Council Licensing Examination (NMCLE), finding that the model achieved a score of 87.8%, an above average showing compared to that of average human medical graduates. However, on deeper analysis, logistic regression revealed that questions requiring logical reasoning were significantly more likely to be answered incorrectly (odds ratio 14.7, 95% CI: 8.94–24.16), while subject area was not an independent predictor after adjusting for question type. The authors note that ChatGPT's strong performance on the NMCLE likely reflects the exclusive use of English in Nepal's medical education, as well as the exam's overall nature on preference to recall-based knowledge testing rather than complex clinical reasoning [18]. Similarly, Chapagain et al. (2024) evaluated multiple LLM models; including GPT-4o, Gemini, Mistral, and LLaMA on Nepal's Higher Secondary Education Board (HSEB) Physics examination, the same Grade 12 curriculum based on which IOE questions are prepared. GPT-4o performed best among the models tested, achieving a score of 90%. However, the authors of the study noted some persistent weaknesses: calculation and unit errors, misinterpretation of physical scenarios, and difficulty with problems that required multi-step reasoning. These findings suggest that even high-performing models may struggle with characteristic of Nepalese entrance exams [19].

On a broader context, the educational research community is trying to make sense of these mixed bag results. A 2025 meta-analysis in *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications* reviewed dozens of studies and suggested that LLMs such as ChatGPT can improve learning in some circumstances, but the the improvement gain depends upon the nature of learning task, the subject, and how the tool is integrated in the learning process. The authors argue that LLMs do not automatically make any students learn better; the benefits only emerge when the surrounding learning environment is well designed [20]. LLM reasoning limitations have also motivated the exploration of coordinated multi-agent approaches. Aryal et al. (2024) showed that domain-specialized AI agents collaborating within a structured workflow outperform single models in complex, cross-disciplinary queries, illustrating how multi-agent frameworks can partially compensate for the gaps in LLM reasoning and long-context synthesis [21].

Compiling all of these together, a clearer picture emerges. LLMs are strong in breadth; they can engage with many topics, often with expert-level fluency, and they can even pass some structured professional exams. But their weaknesses show up when the task demands multi-step, symbol-heavy reasoning or when the format of the question interacts with hidden model biases. For South Asia specifically, the evidence so far is varied: Indian medical exams show promising results, JEE-Advanced exposes serious limitations, and Nepal has only recently begun to be studied. The NMCLE and HSEB Physics evaluations provide some valuable precedents, but neither addresses the specific context of engineering entrance examinations, which combine elements of both: content-heavy recall questions as well as problems requiring nuanced subject understanding.

This creates a research opportunity. We still do not fully understand how LLMs behave on focused standardized exams used for engineering admissions in Nepal. The IOE entrance examination, with its mix of PCME questions, offers a unique test opportunity. Unlike many benchmark datasets, these questions are not officially published even after the examination; hence, to the best of our knowledge, they have not been digitized on the public internet, reducing the contamination concerns that plague many LLM evaluation studies. Studying LLM performance in this environment, with attention to subject-wise patterns and systematic response biases, we hope the study fills a gap in the current literature.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Dataset

The dataset used for this study consisted of 492 multiple-choice questions (MCQs) from PCME. To construct the study set, questions from different mock examinations were compiled as these tests mirror the structure, difficulty, and content distribution of the actual exam and are professionally constructed by subject matter experts. Questions that closely resembled each others were also removed to prevent inflation or deflation of the results. The choice for mocked questions was dictated

since IOE does not officially publish the questions, it has used to conduct the exams, so recalls made by the students are as good as it gets, which often misses some options or framing of the question could be wrong, leading to question quality issues if recall-based questions were to be used. As these questions were not obtained from digital archives, to the best of our knowledge, they have never been published on the internet, thereby avoiding the problem of data in the training sets of the LLMs used.

The distribution of the categories in the question set used to conduct the study is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. No. of Questions for Each Category

Category	No of questions
Maths	176
Physics	134
Chemistry	112
English	70

This section should be detailed enough that readers can replicate your research, and assess whether the methods justify the conclusions. It's advisable to use the past tense – it's about what you did – and avoid using the first person. Ultimately, you should explain how you studied the problem, identify the procedures you followed, and structure this information as logically as possible.

If your methods are new, you'll need to explain them in detail. If they've been published before, cite the original work, including your amendments if you've made modifications. Identify the equipment and the materials you used, specifying their source. State the frequency of observations and what types of data were recorded.

Give precise measurements, stating their strengths and weaknesses when necessary. Name any statistical tests, so your quantitative results can be judged.

If your research involves human participants, you'll need to include certain information in the ethics statement, such as committee approvals and permission to publish. You should also explain your criteria for selecting participants.

Dataset Preparation

Each curated set contained multiple-choice questions from the above-mentioned four subjects or categories, in accordance with the official exam structure. Every question included four answer Options (1–4) and a correct answer key. The original question sets, provided in PDF format, were digitized into a structured JSON schema. As the examination does not indicate which category each question belongs to, questions were assigned a category by domain experts. For programmatic ease, these questions, along with their categories, options, and correct answers, were stored in JSON format with the following keys: Question, Category, Options, and Correct Answer. Subsequently, the correct answer key-value pairs were removed to create masked questions, which were then fed to the LLMs used in this study. To prevent unintentional information leakage, the masking operation was conducted as an independent process. The final prompt presented to LLMs comprised a Question, Category, and Options key in the JSON payload field, along with the system and user instructions, details of which are elaborated upon in a later section on prompt design.

Experimental Design

The models used in this study were gpt-5-2025-08-07, claude-opus-4.1-20250805, gemini-2.5-pro, deepseek-chat, and are referred to by their widely recognized names as ChatGPT, Claude, Gemini, and DeepSeek, respectively, in this paper, and were the SOTA commercially available models at this time. The prompt design process adhered to the principles documented in guidebooks on large language model prompting from the model providers Google [22], Anthropic [23], OpenAI [24], Together AI [25]. Research has demonstrated that one-shot learning techniques, where models are provided with a single illustrative example, yield more effective and consistent responses [26]. Accordingly, each API call incorporated a demonstrative example to guide response formatting and structure.

Prompt Development and Refinement

We start with an initial baseline prompt that consists of straightforward instructions for the models to answer multiple-choice questions and return responses in JSON format. However, early testing revealed some limitations in this approach. Models frequently deviated from the specified output structure, providing answers in varied formats: some using letter designations (a, b, c, d), others using numerical indices (1, 2, 3, 4), and others embedding explanatory text alongside their selections. Additionally, the baseline prompt resulted in an inconsistent answer selection behavior when questions involved numerical approximations or when models encountered unfamiliar content.

These results showed that a prompt refinement process was needed, focusing on three critical dimensions. Firstly, both system and user prompts were made considerably more verbose and explicit, removing ambiguous instructions. Secondly, specific formatting requirements were articulated with greater precision, including explicit directives to maintain JSON structural integrity and to include option numbers in responses. Thirdly, a one-shot example was used to provide models with a concrete template for the expected output format. This example question remained constant across all API calls regardless of the subject domain being tested, as it served a single purpose: guiding the response format.

The refined prompt was validated through pilot testing on multiple questions not included in the study dataset. This refinement enhanced specificity, reduced formatting inconsistencies, and improved adherence to answer selection instructions.

Prompt Architecture and Rationale

To maintain experimental consistency across the used models, identical prompts were used. The prompt contained three components: system instruction, user prompt, and the question itself. The system instruction established the task's base context by positioning the model as a student preparing to take an engineering entrance examination. This student persona served two key objectives: it steered model behavior within the context of examination conditions, and established appropriate uncertainty (acknowledging that students may not know all answers). The user prompt contained operational instructions and question content. Similarly, the output format specification instruction mandated that responses follow the required JSON structure with proper indentation, that the original question text and category be reproduced verbatim, and answers include both the option number and content. The requirement to include option numbers was a practical necessity: models exhibited varied tendencies in their answer representations, and standardizing on option numbers helped with programmatic matching and score calculation during response parsing and analysis.

The prompt also included an instruction to select the option most closely matching their calculated answer when exact matches were unavailable; a strategy often used in actual tests by students to maximize their score. Conversely, instruction was provided to leave the answer field blank when models lacked sufficient confidence in any of the provided four options to avoid score fluctuation arising from random selection. JSON as a response format was chosen as its hierarchical structure accommodated the nested information required (question, category, answer). The complete prompt specification, including both system and user components, is provided in Appendix A.

Experimental Configuration

All models were evaluated at the temperature setting (1.0) to ensure fair comparison across models. While some models allow altering temperature configurations, this setting represented the only readily available option across all tested systems, thereby creating a common experimental baseline. Moreover, early testing showed that the performance of the models was better at this setting than at temp=0, those which supported this parameter, although the improvement was not substantial. As all tested models supported the OpenAI API format specification, this substantially simplified implementation.

Data Quality Assurance

Despite explicit JSON formatting instructions in the prompt, the outputs from the models occasionally deviated from the expected structure and had syntactic inconsistencies, a missing opening brackets at the start of JSON list objects, which prevented valid parsing. Manual corrections were applied to

restore structural validity, but critically, no modifications were made to the semantic content of responses. The selected answers, question text, and category labels remained exactly as produced by each model. Gemini 2.5 Pro fully adhered to formatting specifications, producing structurally valid JSON outputs without requiring manual intervention. The other models exhibited varying frequencies of formatting deviations, though the errors were minuscule.

RESULTS

The evaluation of four LLMs on the IOE entrance examination questions revealed a notable performance tier. Gemini achieved the highest score at 85.77% points (422/492 correct responses), followed closely by ChatGPT at 83.13% (409/492) and Claude at 82.11% (404/492). DeepSeek's model had a comparatively lower performance at 77.24% (380/492). It is worth noting that all models exceeded the ~65% cutoff required for admission to the recently concluded admission session at the flagship campus, indicating an above-average competency in handling IOE entrance examination content. The models exhibited varying non-response rates. ChatGPT had the highest non-response rate at 3.86% (19/492), followed by Gemini at 1.22% (6/492), DeepSeek at 0.61% (3/492), and Claude at 0.41% (2/492). Figure 1 presents the overall percentage point scored by each model. The vertical dashed line represents the cutoff threshold. All four models exceeded this threshold.

Figure 1. Overall Accuracy Comparison across the Four LLMs. The Vertical Dashed Line Marks the Cutoff Threshold for Flagship Campus Admission

The performance gap between the top-performing model (Gemini) and the lowest-performing model (DeepSeek) is approximately 8.5 percentage points.

Subject-category-wise analysis showed consistent performance hierarchies across all four models (a detailed breakdown is presented in Appendix B). Chemistry consistently yielded the highest percentage point scored, with models achieving between 85.71% (DeepSeek) and 92.86% (Gemini). Physics demonstrated the second-strongest performance range (78.36% to 88.81%), followed by English (74.29% to 84.29%). Mathematics questions proved more challenging across all models, with scores spanning 72.16% (DeepSeek) to 80.11% (Gemini) as demonstrated in Figure 2.

Individual model performance exhibited notable category-specific variations. Claude achieved its strongest showing in Physics (88.81%), matching Gemini's performance in that domain, while demonstrating relatively weaker performance in Mathematics (73.30%). ChatGPT maintained a more balanced performance across categories with less variance between its strongest (Chemistry, 91.07%) and weakest (English, 80.00%).

Figure 2. Category-Wise Accuracy Comparison. All Models Exhibit a Similar Performance Ordering: Chemistry, then Physics, then English, and Mathematics

When models provided incorrect answers, somewhat systematic patterns emerged in their option preferences, though the statistical significance of these biases varied considerably. Across all models, Option 1 and 2 (i.e., answers at positions 1 and 2) were disproportionately selected when answers were incorrect. DeepSeek chose answer at position 1 in 29.4% of incorrect cases and position 2 in 33.9% of cases, compared to expected proportions of 25.6% and 24.4%, respectively (adjusted for the actual correct-answer position distribution in the dataset). Claude showed similar tendencies with 32.6% selecting position 1 versus an expected 25.6%. Answers at positions 3 and 4 were consistently under-selected relative to their availability as incorrect choices.

Chi-square tests evaluating whether these answer position selection patterns deviated from expected distributions yielded mixed results. Only DeepSeek demonstrated statistically significant positional bias ($\chi^2 = 8.56$, $p = 0.036$), with particular over-selection of answer at position 2 by approximately 10 selections above expectation. ChatGPT ($\chi^2 = 2.28$, $p = 0.517$), Claude ($\chi^2 = 3.98$, $p = 0.263$), and Gemini ($\chi^2 = 0.58$, $p = 0.901$) exhibited position preference patterns that, while directionally consistent with DeepSeek's bias, did not reach conventional significance thresholds.

We also quantified the relative contributions of model choice, question category, and correct answer position to response accuracy by constructing a logistic regression model using 1,888 observations from 472 questions; 20 questions that had missing responses were excluded in the calculation process. The model treated response correctness as the binary outcome variable, with ChatGPT, Chemistry, and position 1 serving as reference categories.

Model selection emerged as a significant predictor of percentage points scored. Relative to ChatGPT, Gemini showed modestly improved odds of correct responses (OR = 1.23, 95% CI: [1.01, 1.48]), while Claude demonstrated slightly reduced odds (OR = 0.86, 95% CI: [0.71, 1.05]) and DeepSeek substantially lower odds (OR = 0.61, 95% CI: [0.49, 0.74]). These odds ratios (OR) align with the earlier score rankings, providing statistical confirmation of the observed performance differences.

Question category also proved to be a predictor of points scored. Compared to Chemistry (reference category), Mathematics questions showed a significant negative effect (OR = 0.37, 95% CI: [0.29, 0.49]), indicating that models were 62.6% less likely to answer math questions correctly when controlling for other factors. English (OR = 0.45, 95% CI: [0.33, 0.62]) and Physics (OR = 0.69, 95% CI: [0.53, 0.90]) also demonstrated reduced odds relative to Chemistry, though less severely than Mathematics. These findings quantitatively align with the category difficulty hierarchy observed in descriptive statistics.

The position of the correct answer within the four options revealed an interesting pattern. Questions with the correct answer at position 4 showed substantially elevated odds of correct model responses (OR = 1.78, 95% CI: [1.39, 2.29]), representing a 78.4% increase compared to position 1. Examination of raw accuracy by position confirmed this effect: models averaged 89.6% accuracy on position 4 questions compared to 82.4% for position 1, 82.6% for position 2, and 80.5% for position 3. This advantage persisted across all four models, with ChatGPT (95.7%) and Gemini (96.8%) achieving particularly high accuracy when the correct answer occupied position 4.

The overall logistic regression model achieved 84.96% training accuracy, indicating a reasonable fit to the observed data. Model diagnostics (detailed in Appendix B) confirmed acceptable calibration and no severe multicollinearity among predictors.

DISCUSSION

The category-wise performance hierarchy presents a counterintuitive finding that warrants careful examination. The relatively weak performance in Mathematics aligns with existing literature documenting persistent challenges in LLMs' mathematical tasks capabilities [27]. However, English, despite containing no special symbols or subject-specific notations, fared worse than Chemistry across all models. This is surprising given that Chemistry questions do feature chemical formulas, equations, and specialized notation that are widely considered a hindrance to LLM performance.

On a closer look at the response of the models in English, we observed that the questions with wrong responses include the task of reading comprehension, such as suggesting the title for a given text, identifying the core topic of the text and similarly where multiple answers were present. Similarly, the models also struggled on the tasks related to syllabification and counting the number of vowels and consonants on a given sentence, these stem from the way LLMs process the tokens and have been a topic of active research [28].

A higher Chemistry and Physics score suggests two possible interpretations. First, the widely considered notation-based difficulties may be less severe than anticipated for current model generations, suggesting that improvements have been made over time in handling scientific notation. Alternatively, the conceptual demands of English comprehension questions in this dataset may pose distinct challenges beyond symbol complexity alone. English questions in entrance examinations often require a nuanced understanding of context, idiomatic expressions, and subtle semantic distinctions that may prove more challenging for LLMs than the more structured, rule-based reasoning required in Chemistry. The invariance of this ordering, Chemistry > Physics > English > Mathematics, across all four models suggests that question difficulty or content characteristics, rather than model-specific capabilities, primarily determined category performance. This consistency indicates shared strengths and limitations in how current LLMs process different domain knowledge when constrained to multiple-choice formats.

The position 4 advantage identified in the logistic regression analysis (OR = 1.78) represents an interesting finding of this study. While the mechanism underlying this pattern remains speculative without access to model internals. One plausible interpretation is that when evaluating multiple-choice options sequentially, models may apply increasing confidence to later options if earlier ones have been implicitly or explicitly rejected. If the model internally assesses Options 1-3 as unlikely or inconsistent with the question, Option 4 gains probability mass by elimination even in cases where the model lacks strong positive evidence for that choice. This would be consistent with how human test-takers often employ elimination strategies when they are uncertain about all four options presented to them.

However, this hypothesis must be viewed with caution, and alternative explanations cannot be ruled out without further investigation. For instance, the questions in this dataset with correct answers at position 4 may possess distinctive characteristics; perhaps they genuinely are easier, or maybe the incorrect options (positions 1-3) for these questions are more obviously wrong—that could account for the elevated accuracy independent of any sequential elimination process. Without a detailed, controlled experiment that changes answer positions while holding question content constant, we cannot isolate the causal mechanism. However, what remains clear is that answer position does exert an influence on model accuracy that exists across all four models examined.

The chi-square analysis revealed that only DeepSeek demonstrated statistically significant positional bias when selecting incorrect answers ($\chi^2 = 8.56$, $p = 0.036$), while others showed a similar pattern directionally, that failed to reach any thresholds. This raises questions about what distinguishes DeepSeek's decision-making process from the rest. Several factors may contribute to this discrepancy.

First, DeepSeek's higher overall error rate did provide a greater statistical power to detect biases that may exist but remain undetectable in smaller samples. The fact that all four models showed numerically similar patterns; with options in positions 1 and 2 over-selected and positions 3 and 4 under-selected, suggests the bias may be prevalent but only shows statistical significance when sufficient errors accumulate.

Second, architectural or training differences specific to DeepSeek may genuinely produce stronger positional biases in its response generation process. The consistent over-selection of position 2 by approximately 10 selections above expectation suggests a systematic tendency that could reflect how the model weights early options during evaluation. Whether this stems from tokenization schemes, implementation of attention mechanisms, or peculiarities in training data distribution remains unclear to us at this time.

The broader implication of these option position preference patterns is that models do not select incorrect answers uniformly across available positions. When uncertain, these models appear to lean toward earlier options in the presentation sequence. This has practical consequences if such models are used for answer assessment in future. If models systematically favor certain positions when guessing, their performance on tests with non-random correct answer distributions could be artificially inflated or deflated depending on how test creators position correct responses. If such models are to be used in automated grading systems, any evaluators should be aware that option order may introduce subtle confounds into score earned.

The finding that all four models exceeded the 65% cutoff threshold suggests that current LLMs are in fact capable of handling IOE entrance examination and have above average performance doing so.

These results suggest a direction of LLMs serving as practice partners for students preparing for entrance examinations, providing immediate feedback on a substantial majority of questions. The 77-86% accuracy range is sufficient for identifying students' weak areas and generating practice problems.

LIMITATIONS

Several limitations constrain wider generalizability and interpretation of our findings. First, even though we have tried to generalize the dataset, performance patterns may differ if there is change in question styles, and difficulty distributions. Secondly, while all questions were manually inspected for accuracy, visual elements such as circuit diagrams were converted to textual representations rather than being presented as images. This transformation may have introduced ambiguity or increased difficulty for questions originally designed with visual components. Thirdly, we evaluated models with system instructions that explicitly encouraged guessing when uncertain, mirroring real examination conditions. Alternative prompting might alter performance patterns.

FUTURE WORKS

Several pathways for future research could emerge from these findings. Firstly, the counterintuitive under performance of English warrants deeper investigation. Investigating whether this reflects genuine limitations in language understanding, oddities of questions, or architectural features of how LLMs process different content types could be informational. Secondly, examining the relationship between model confidence scores and actual correctness could provide insights into when LLMs are reliable versus when they produce confident but incorrect responses. Such calibration analyses would be particularly valuable in critical educational settings where knowing when to trust model outputs is critical.

CONCLUSION

This study evaluated four large language models; ChatGPT, Claude, Gemini, and DeepSeek; on multiple-choice questions from the IOE entrance exam. All models easily exceeded the admission cutoff threshold, with percentage point scores ranging from 77.24% (DeepSeek) to 85.77% (Gemini). Subject-category-wise analysis revealed a consistent performance hierarchy across all models: Chemistry (85.71-92.86%) > Physics (78.36-88.81%) > English (74.29-84.29%) > Mathematics (72.16-80.11%). Notably, English underperformed Chemistry and Physics despite lacking complex notation, contrary to expectations from prior literature on scientific notations processing difficulties.

Statistical analysis identified systematic patterns in model behavior. Chi-square tests revealed significant option selection bias only in DeepSeek ($\chi^2 = 8.56$, $p = 0.036$), with disproportionate selection of options in position 1 and 2 when answering incorrectly. Logistic regression demonstrated that questions with correct answers at position 4 had substantially elevated odds of correct responses (OR = 1.78), an effect persisting across most all models, barring DeepSeek. Non-response rates varied considerably, with ChatGPT refusing 3.86% of questions compared to less than 1.22% for other models.

These findings demonstrate that current LLMs do excel at the IOE entrance exam but still exhibit some systematic biases in option selection and position-dependent accuracy patterns.

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APPENDIX

Appendix A: Prompt Specification

The prompts used in this study comprised two components: a system instruction and a main user prompt. Both remained identical across all model evaluations to ensure experimental consistency.

System Instruction

You are a student going to appear in a multiple choice entrance exam for an engineering college. Answer the question as correctly as you can to increase your score and thus chances to get in. Please strictly follow the instructions given in the question and the formatting of the output requested.

Main Prompt

For each of the questions provided below, select the correct answer from the list of the given options. Provide the return output in the same json format as the question. Strictly follow the JSON rule for formatting, i.e. with indentations too as required. (NO EXCEPTIONS)

First repeat the question and the category of the question as it is provided to you then provide the answer in the answer field.

Do not repeat the options in your response.

Provide the answer in the same physical unit of measurement as which is listed on the question.

If the exact answer is not listed on the given options, select the option which you think is closest.

If you do not find appropriate answer for the given question in the provided options leave the answer blank in your response.

Do not provide any explanations or reasoning in your response. Just strictly follow the format as asked.

One sample of expected response from you is as follow:

```
{  
  'question': 'If he had heard the news,.....',  
  'category': 'English',  
  'answer': '4. he would have telephoned me'  
},
```

In your response do not forget to include the option number (don't just provide the answer only)

The questions and options are as follows:

The questions were presented as JSON objects appended to this prompt, with each object containing the question text, category, and four numbered options

Appendix B: Detailed Statistical Results

B.1 Category-wise Performance Breakdown

Table A1 presents the complete breakdown of correct and incorrect responses for each model across all four subject categories.

Table A1. Detailed Category-Wise Performance Showing Correct and Incorrect Response Counts

Category	Model	Correct	Incorrect
Math (176)	DeepSeek	127 (72.16%)	49 (27.84%)
	ChatGPT	136 (77.27%)	40 (22.73%)
	Claude	129 (73.30%)	47 (26.70%)
	Gemini	141 (80.11%)	35 (19.89%)
Physics (134)	DeepSeek	105 (78.36%)	29 (21.64%)
	ChatGPT	115 (85.82%)	19 (14.18%)
	Claude	119 (88.81%)	15 (11.19%)
	Gemini	118 (88.06%)	16 (11.94%)
English (70)	DeepSeek	52 (74.29%)	18 (25.71%)
	ChatGPT	56 (80.00%)	14 (20.00%)
	Claude	57 (81.43%)	13 (18.57%)
	Gemini	59 (84.29%)	11 (15.71%)
Chemistry (112)	DeepSeek	96 (85.71%)	16 (14.29%)
	ChatGPT	102 (91.07%)	10 (8.93%)
	Claude	99 (88.39%)	13 (11.61%)
	Gemini	104 (92.86%)	8 (7.14%)

Figure A1 visualizes the correct versus incorrect response distribution across all categories and models.

B.2 Logistic Regression Analysis Details

The logistic regression model included 1,888 observations from 472 questions (excluding questions with missing responses). Table A2 summarizes the dataset composition for the regression model.

The logistic regression used ChatGPT, Chemistry, and Position 1 as reference categories. Table A3 presents the complete regression results with coefficients, odds ratios, and confidence intervals.

B.3 Accuracy by Correct Answer Position

Table A4 details model performance stratified by the position of the correct answer, revealing the substantial advantage when correct answers appear at position 4.

Table A2. Dataset Composition for Logistic Regression Analysis

Factor	Correct Responses	Score Points (%)
Model		
ChatGPT	409/472	86.65
Claude	400/472	84.75
DeepSeek	376/472	79.66
Gemini	419/472	88.77
Category		
Chemistry	400/436	91.74
English	224/272	82.35
Math	527/664	79.37
Physics	453/516	87.79
Correct Answer Position		
Position 1	374	-
Position 2	415	-
Position 3	478	-
Position 4	337	-

Table A3. Complete Logistic Regression Results Predicting Correct Responses

Feature	Coefficient	Odds Ratio	Effect (%)
Model Effects (ref: ChatGPT)			
Gemini	0.205	1.227	22.7
Claude	-0.147	0.863	-13.7
DeepSeek	-0.503	0.605	-39.5

Category Effects (ref: Chemistry)			
Physics	-0.369	0.691	-30.9
English	-0.795	0.451	-54.9
Math	-0.985	0.374	-62.6
Position Effects (ref: Position 1)			
Position 4	0.579	1.784	78.4
Position 2	-0.002	0.998	-0.2
Position 3	-0.038	0.963	-3.7
Model training accuracy: 84.96%			

Table A4. Model Accuracy Stratified by Correct Answer Position

Model	Position 1 (n=114)	Position 2 (n=132)	Position 3 (n=152)	Position 4 (n=94)
DeepSeek	86/114 (75.4%)	109/130 (83.8%)	111/151 (73.5%)	74/94 (78.7%)
ChatGPT	99/113 (87.6%)	101/124 (81.5%)	120/143 (83.9%)	89/93 (95.7%)
Claude	92/114 (80.7%)	108/131 (82.4%)	121/151 (80.1%)	83/94 (88.3%)
Gemini	98/114 (86.0%)	107/129 (82.9%)	126/149 (84.6%)	91/94 (96.8%)
Average	82.40%	82.60%	80.50%	89.60%

Figure A1. Category-Wise Breakdown of Correct (Green) and Incorrect (Red) Responses across All Four Models. Each Subplot Shows the Distribution for One Subject Category

